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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF NUTRIMENT- D INSUFFICIENCY IN
VICTIMS APPEARING THE DRUG O-P-D OF SIR GANGA
RAM HOSPITAL, LAHORE, PAKISTAN****¹Dr. Faryal Afridi, ²Dr Kashif Mehmood, ³Dr. Waqas Riaz Ahmad**¹Avicenna Hospital Lahore, ²DHO Office Sudhnuti AJK, ³Service Institute of Medical Sciences**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Aim: To regulate the regularity of nutriment- D insufficiency in victims with twinges and discomfort in the physique.
Methods Place and Duration: A total of 120 victims were included in the research. In the Sir Ganga Ram Hospital for six months' duration from October 2018 to March 2019. A random non-probable sampling technique was used and the approval from the ethical committee was taken.

Results: Of the 80 victims, 56 (70%) had a nutriment- D insufficiency (30 ng / ml). 80 of 120 victims (66.8%) were women and 40 (33.7%) were men.

Conclusion: Compared to other parts of the world there is more insufficiency and the prevalence of nutriment- D insufficiency is upper in victims with fatigue.

Key words: victims with O-P-D, body twinges, nutriment- D insufficiency,

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INTRODUCTION:

This phenomenon is intensifying. Complaints about easy fatigue are more common today than ever. He can talk to any seemingly healthy victim or person and has complaints about drowsiness and little resistance. Some drugs, such as alcoholism, sedatives and beta-blockers, can cause a similar clinical picture. Important syndromes that can cause fatigue are thyroid complaints, endocrine syndromes such as diabetes and chronic obstructive airway syndrome, chronic infections (e.g. chronic hepatitis, infective endocarditis), congestive heart failure, anemia, autoimmune complaints and cancer. They can also cause drowsiness and body twinges. Overcooking disrupts the nutriment- D content of these sources. It has been reported that over 85% of people in our region suffer from nutriment- D insufficiency / insufficiency (<30 mg / ml). Finally, fibromyalgia, depression and sleep complaints etc. Mental situations such as. Recently, clinical trials have reported a risk of nutriment- D insufficiency.

Nutriment- D insufficiency is not only associated with metabolic bone syndrome such as osteomalacia and rickets, it can also occur with mild fatigue without signs of osteopenia. This exceeds secondary to fatigue, physical illness and drugs whose cause is unknown or associated with mental illness. Nutriment- D, also called "solar nutriment-", is a hormone produced on our skin in its original form, pro-nutriment- D (7 deoxy cholesterol), which is first hydroxylated in the liver and then in the liver after exposure to sunlight. It

works at the level of mitochondria in muscle inflammation, affects cellular respiration and causes fatigue. In many cases labeled fibromyalgia, they actually lacked nutriment- D and were still diagnosed as out of the question. This is the most important source of nutriment- D for humans.⁹ Other sources of nutriment- D include fungi and fatty fish. Kidneys (1.25 dihydroxycholesterol) to produce nutriment- D activity.

VICTIMS AND METHODS:

A total of 120 victims were included in the research. A random non-probable sampling technique was used and the approval from the ethical committee was taken. This Prospective research was held in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital for six months duration from October 2018 to March 2019.

RESULTS:

25 of 40 males (62.5%) had nutriment- D insufficiency (<20ng / ml) and 8 of 40 men (20%) had nutriment- D insufficiency (21-29ng / ml). Eighty (66.7%) of 120 victims are women and 40 (33.5%) are men. Of the 80 victims, 56 (70%) had nutriment- D insufficiency (<20 ng / ml) and 14 of 80 victims (17.6%) had nutriment- D insufficiency (21-29 ng / ml). A total of 103 (85.7%) of 120 victims suffered from nutriment- D insufficiency / insufficiency (<30ng / ml). 17 out of 120 victims (14.5%) had adequate nutriment- D stages (≥ 30 ng / dl). Therefore, 81 (67.6%) of 120 victims had nutriment- D insufficiency (<20ng / ml) and 22 (18.5%) nutriment- D insufficiency (21-29ng / ml).

Table 1: Nutriment- D Insufficiency & Insufficiency

Gender	Total	Nutriment- D Insufficiency	Nutriment- D Insufficiency	Total Nutriment- D Insufficiency & Insufficiency
Masculine	40	25(63.0%)	8(20.0)	33(27.7%)
Feminine	80	56(70.0%)	14(18.0%)	70(58.35%)

DISCUSSION:

One research found that the prevalence of nutriment- D insufficiency in primary care clinics is 45%. The research showed that most victims with fatigue had low stages of nutriment- D. This is confirmed by international and national literature on the subject. These included low nutriment- D stages in 1/3 of Norwegian Norwegians in the Middle East, Africa and South Asia, and 83% of victims visiting the Abbasi Shaheed Karachi Hospital. Another multiethnic general practice research found nutriment- D insufficiency in 58% of victims. In another research in adult victims in an outvictim clinic, nutriment- D stages were low in 89.3% and 16.1% of victims with nutriment- D insufficiency in 73.2%. The frequency of

nutriment- D insufficiency was 92%. This is the same number as in the survey. Aslam *et al.* noticed a similar percentage (92.85%) in Faisalabad studies at a prenatal clinic. The habit of chewing betel nuts has been accused by modulating the activity of enzymes that regulate plasma circulation stages in Asians with a density of 1.25 OH D.21, with pigmented skin, despite too much sun exposure. About nutriment- D insufficiency. This can be explained by the fact that a high degree of contamination prevents the penetration of ultraviolet rays into human skin. The cycle of nutriment--D absorption is shown in the figure. Much lower nutriment- D content than in European and American populations.

One research found that 69% of victims suffered from nutrient- D insufficiency, which was slightly upper but closer to our research. This difference may be due to different dietary factors and nutrient- D content in the diet in different regions. Eighty-one (67.6%) of the 120 victims in our research had nutrient- D insufficiency (<20ng / ml).

Dental health support

Oral supplements of vitamin D3 may help to keep your teeth healthy.

Bone health support

Oral vitamin D3 supplements may help support the natural ability of bones to maintain their normal hardness. This is especially beneficial in the presence of liver conditions that cause bones to soften.

Cardio support

Recent studies indicate that Vitamin D3 can help restore cardiovascular endothelial cells which are already damaged [1].

Calcium support

Vitamin D3 may help to support healthy levels of calcium in the blood. Low calcium levels can result from some types of poor kidney function.

Phosphate support

Vitamin D3 may help to maintain phosphate levels, which can result from some genetic disorders.

To a small extent, these results are slightly less comparable than in the research in 40 women, who constitute 80% and 20% of victims suffering from O-P-D insufficiency and failure with fibromyalgia. Nutrient- D. In our research, 56 (70%) of 80 women had nutrient- D insufficiency (<20 ng / ml), and 14 (17.5%) of women had nutrient- D insufficiency. O-P-D was diagnosed with physical discomfort and fibromyalgia. He was deficient in nutrient- D. 75 women with premenopausal tibial discomfort and general discomfort and discomfort reported to a third-level care center in Lahore, Pakistan. This small difference may be due to the smaller working size. In our research, the results of nutrient- D insufficiency in women can be compared with the research in which 56 (70%) of 80 victims and 53 (74%) Mufti et al.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of nutrient- D insufficiency is upper in victims with fatigue than in other parts of the world.

REFERENCES:

1. Khalife, Roy, Anthony Grieco, Karima Khamisa, Alan Tinmouh, Chris McCudden, and Elianna Saidenberg. "Scurvy, an old story in a new time: The hematologist's experience." *Plasma Cells, Molecules, and Syndromes* 76 (2019): 40-44. Khalife, R., Grieco, A., Khamisa, K., Tinmouh, A., McCudden, C. and Saidenberg, E., 2019. Scurvy, an old story in a new time: The hematologist's experience. *Plasma Cells, Molecules, and Syndromes*, 76, pp.40-44.
2. CHAMOLI, RP, GAURAV BAHUGUNA, and ARVIND MOHAN DISCOMFORTULY. "MIRACULOUS PHYSIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF NUTRIMENT- D AND ITS ROLE IN HUMAN HEALTH AND SYNDROMES." *SCIENCE AND CULTURE* (2019). CHAMOLI, R., BAHUGUNA, G. and DISCOMFORTULY, A.M., 2019. MIRACULOUS PHYSIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF NUTRIMENT- D AND ITS ROLE IN HUMAN HEALTH AND SYNDROMES. *SCIENCE AND CULTURE*.
3. Anadure, R. K., S. Shankar, Aneesh Mohimen, Arpitha Pemmaraju, and Jitumani Kalita. "An unusual case of eosinophilia, myalgia and skin contractures: Shulman's syndrome revisited." *Medical Journal Armed Forces India* (2020).
4. Fatima, Lubna, Arun Kumar Bhadula, L. Janani, Izharul Hasan, Divya Saraswat, Kanak Soni, Tushita Thakur, and Ashish Kumar Dixit. "A Compilation of Case Reports from Ayush Wellness Clinic, President's Estate, New Delhi, India." *Journal of AYUSH* 7, no. 1 (2018): 14-26. Fatima, L., Bhadula, A.K., Janani, L., Hasan, I., Saraswat, D., Soni, K., Thakur, T. and Dixit, A.K., 2018. A Compilation of Case Reports from Ayush Wellness Clinic, President's Estate, New Delhi, India. *Journal of AYUSH*, 7(1), pp.14-26.
5. Mastrangelo, F., I. Frydas, G. Ronconi, S. K. Kritas, L. Tettamanti, Al Caraffa, C. D Ovidio, A. Younes, C. E. Gallenga, and P. Conti. "Low-grade chronic inflammation mediated by mast cells in fibromyalgia: role of IL-37." *J Biol Regul Homeost Agents* 32, no. 2 (2018): 195-198.
6. Jensen, Sara Albrechtsen, Henrik Højgaard Rasmussen, Annette Engsig, and Mette Holst. "Nutritional impact symptoms evoking unintended weight loss among elderly victims in general practice." *Integrative Clinical Drug and Therapeutics* 1, no. 2 (2018). Jensen, S.A., Rasmussen, H.H., Engsig, A. and Holst, M., 2018. Nutritional impact symptoms evoking unintended weight loss among elderly victims in general practice. *Integrative Clinical Drug and Therapeutics*, 1(2).
7. Booyesen, Naomi. "An analysis of diagnosed conditions and treatment frequency in victims presenting to the UJ chiropractic clinic in 2016." PhD diss., University of Johannesburg, 2019. Booyesen, N., 2019. *An analysis of diagnosed conditions and treatment frequency in victims presenting to the UJ chiropractic clinic in 2016* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Johannesburg).
8. Arnold, Lesley M., Robert M. Bennett, Leslie J. Crofford, Linda E. Dean, Daniel J. Clauw, Don L. Goldenberg, Mary-Ann Fitzcharles et al. "AAPT diagnostic criteria for fibromyalgia." *The Journal of Discomfort* 20, no. 6 (2019): 611-628. Arnold, L.M., Bennett, R.M., Crofford, L.J., Dean, L.E., Clauw, D.J., Goldenberg, D.L., Fitzcharles, M.A., Paiva, E.S., Staud, R., Sarzi-Puttini, P. and Buskila, D., 2019. AAPT diagnostic criteria for fibromyalgia. *The Journal of Discomfort*, 20(6), pp.611-628.
9. Rajabi-Naeeni, Masoumeh, Mahrokh Dolatian, Mostafa Qorbani, and Amir Abbas Vaezi. "The effect of co supplementation of omega-3 and nutrient- D on cardio metabolic risk factors and psychological distress in reproductive-aged women with prediabetes and hyponutrient-osis D: a research protocol for a randomized controlled trial." *Trials* 20, no. 1 (2019): 799.
10. de Carvalho Alves, Rafaela, Victor Rodrigues Nepomuceno, Florence Germaine Tible Lainscek, and Pricila Zancanella. "Impact of Fibromyalgia on the Quality of Life of Victims in

- Brazil." *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science* 6, no. 5 (2019).
11. Karaduman, A., I. Alemdaroğlu Gürbüz, E. Acar Aslan, M. Güngör, N. Bulut, G. Aydın, Ö. Yılmaz, B. Talim, and H. Topaloğlu. "DUCHENNE MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY–CLINICAL: P. 14The profile of Duchenne muscular dystrophy victims younger than 10 years old from KUKAS registry, Turkey." *Neuromuscular Complaints* 28 (2018): S35-S36.
 12. NANDAM, MOHAN RAO, Shanthi ViSSa, SyaM SundaRa Rao Byna, BhaVana GRandhi, and Sujitha RaGuRaMan. "An Unusual Presentation of Ochronosis with Palmar Pigmentation." *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research* 13, no. 9 (2019). NANDAM, M.R., ViSSa, S., Byna, S.S.R., GRandhi, B. and RaGuRaMan, S., 2019. An Unusual Presentation of Ochronosis with Palmar Pigmentation. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*, 13(9).
 13. ZAKIR, SHAIK MOHAMMAD, ABHISHEK AGRAWAL, SAIYID N. ASKARI, and SHAMIM AHMAD. "Prophylactic Effect of Topical Besifloxacin and Moxifloxacin on the Bacterial Conjunctival Flora Before and After Intraocular Surgery." *IJCP Group of Publications* 29, no. 12 (2019): 1160.
 14. Bawaskar, Himmatrao S., Pramodini H. Bawaskar, and Parag H. Bawaskar. "Preintensive care: thrombolytic (streptokinase or tenecteplase) in ST elevated acute myocardial infarction at peripheral hospital." *Journal of family drug and primary care* 8, no. 1 (2019): 62. Bawaskar, H.S., Bawaskar, P.H. and Bawaskar, P.H., 2019. Preintensive care: thrombolytic (streptokinase or tenecteplase) in ST elevated acute myocardial infarction at peripheral hospital. *Journal of family drug and primary care*, 8(1), p.62.
 15. Eusterman, Vincent D., Katharine G. Meddles, B. Viswanatha, Francisco Talavera, Robert M. Kellman, and Christopher L. Slack. "Burning mouth syndrome." *Online document at: <http://edrug.medscape.com/article/1508869-overview#showall>* Accessed January 14 (2019). Eusterman, V.D., Meddles, K.G., Viswanatha, B., Talavera, F., Kellman, R.M. and Slack, C.L., 2019. Burning mouth syndrome. *Online document at: <http://edrug.medscape.com/article/1508869-overview#showall>* Accessed January, 14.
 16. Dubale, Amanuel. "Prevalence of Nutrient- D Insufficiency and Associated Risk Factors Among Victims with Nonspecific Musculoskeletal Discomfort Symptoms Appearing Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia." PhD diss., Addis Ababa University, 2019.
 17. Syed, Muhammad Azfar, Syeda Rubaba Azim, and Mukhtiar Baig. "Frequency of orthopedic problems among victims appearing an orthopedic outvictim department: a retrospective analysis of 23 495 cases." *Annals of Saudi Drug* 39, no. 3 (2019): 172-177. Syed, M.A., Azim, S.R. and Baig, M., 2019. Frequency of orthopedic problems among victims appearing an orthopedic outvictim department: a retrospective analysis of 23 495 cases. *Annals of Saudi Drug*, 39(3), pp.172-177.
 18. Ince, Bilsev, Mehmet Emin Sakarya, and Mehmet Dadaci. "An assessment of the effects of serum nutrient- d stages on snoring in victims who have undergone septorhinoplasty." *Turkish Journal of Plastic Surgery* 26, no. 2 (2018): 50. Ince, B., Sakarya, M.E. and Dadaci, M., 2018. An assessment of the effects of serum nutrient- d stages on snoring in victims who have undergone septorhinoplasty. *Turkish Journal of Plastic Surgery*, 26(2), p.50.